

Training on use of AQUARIUS Access Platform

OGS, National Institute of Oceanography and Applied
Geophysics

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1. Executive Summary

The AQUARIUS project, funded by Horizon Europe, provides Transnational Access (TA) to marine and freshwater research infrastructure. To facilitate this, AQUARIUS developed the Transnational Access Platform (TAP), an online tool managing all aspects of TA, from proposal submission to project reporting. Training on TAP, organized under Work Package 3, Task 3.4, was scheduled alongside the First Transnational Access call on November 11, 2024.

A webinar was conducted to guide researchers through the call submission process and platform usage. The session was recorded and made available on the AQUARIUS website and Training Hub, ensuring continued accessibility. The webinar was also widely promoted through the project's outreach programme (WP7).

2. Introduction

AQUARIUS Work Package 3 “RI Call Design, Management, Evaluation and Access Platform” is responsible for the design, development and management of the calls for transnational access to the AQUARIUS research infrastructure through a robust scientific and logistical review process to formulate and prioritise the challenges for marine and freshwater ecosystems and ensure easy access through a tailored and user-friendly platform.

The AQUARIUS Transnational Access Platform (TAP) serves as a centralized access point for managing TA proposals. It was developed by extending and integrating previous access procedures and platforms, leveraging experience from INTERACT, ARICE, and Eurofleets—prior EU TA projects.

The objective of Work Package 5 (RI Technical Training) is to equip researchers with the necessary skills, tools, and guidance to effectively access and utilize research infrastructures. This is achieved through:

- Ad hoc training tailored to specific research infrastructures (RIs)
- Training needs and gaps analysis to ensure efficient RI usage
- Data stewardship & open science training
- Training on accessing and using the TAP

To support ongoing education, the AQUARIUS Training Hub has been established. It includes:

- Training resources from AQUARIUS and other Horizon 2020 & Horizon Europe projects
- Topics covering marine & freshwater ecosystem protection, zero pollution, and a sustainable blue economy
- Digital e-learning resources, including tools, presentations, and webinars
- Guidance on data management & virtual research environments

As part of Task 5.2, a webinar was organized to train users on the AQUARIUS Transnational Access Platform, covering: how to access and use the AQUARIUS Transnational Access Platform, including reporting training needs. The objective of the training was to assist applicants to submit high quality proposals while ensuring all of the eligibility criteria were met.

The webinar was recorded and is available on the [AQUARIUS Training Hub](#) for future AQUARIUS Calls.

3. Organization and webinar development

3.1. Webinar organization

The webinar was organised by WP5 (OGS) in collaboration with WP2 & 4 (MI), WP3 (AWI, CNR, INKODE) and WP7 (SSBE).

The webinar was scheduled to align with the opening of the first AQUARIUS TA call (Regional Lighthouse Access Call) which opened on 11 November 2024 and closed on 20 January 2025. After some meetings with the partners involved in the webinar organization, it was agreed to schedule the webinar shortly after the first call opened to give potential users some time to register on the TAP, learn about the call requirements and to get somewhat familiar with the TAP so that any initial queries could be addressed during the webinar. For this reason, the webinar was scheduled two (2) weeks after the opening of the call, on the 27th November 2024.

OGS met with the partners on 12 November 2024 to determine the agenda, topics and speakers for the webinar “Training on the use of the AQUARIUS Access Platform”. The following agenda was agreed upon in order to give participants a comprehensive overview of the available infrastructures, call design, application process, eligibility and evaluation criteria.

Table 1: Agenda of the webinar

Presentation	Presenter	Time (CET)	Organization
Welcome & Intro	A. Caburlotto	11:00	OGS
AQUARIUS Infrastructure Catalogue	F. Armstrong	11:05	MI
Call Design & Eligibility Criteria	L. Evangelista	11:10	CNR
How to use the Call Platform	A. Strobel & E. De Maio	11:20	AWI & INKODE
Evaluation Process	Anneli Strobel	11:40	AWI
Q&A Session	All	11:50	

The upcoming webinar was widely disseminated via AQUARIUS social media channels, website subscribers and project contacts. SSBE set up the webinar platform using Zoom and handled the registration and outreach. Those interested in participating could register via the AQUARIUS website and using the link provided in social media posts.

Figure 1 Social Media and website posts announcing the webinar

3.2. Webinar Training “Learn to use the call application platform”

The training webinar on “How to Use the call application platform” was held on 27 November 2024. The webinar was organised and recorded by SSBE (WP7) using the Zoom platform.

The attendees’ cameras and microphones were disabled throughout, and they were asked to post all questions using the Q&A chat function.

The speakers and the topics were introduced by OGS, as moderator of the webinar:

1. Frank Armstrong (MI) introduced the AQUARIUS project, the thematic and geographical scopes, the Research Infrastructure Catalogue and the type of access (remote, physical) and the travel and logistic budget.
2. Anneli Strobel (AWI) presented the Call design and Eligibility Criteria on behalf of Lorenza Evangelista (CNR), who was unable to be present, and explained the AQUARIUS support, ambition, how the AQUARIUS TA call was designed, and the eligibility criteria required to apply.
3. Anneli Strobel presented the application process and the appendices required; Elizabeth De Maio (INKODE) explained the workflow of the TA call platform, from the registration to the submission of the reports.
4. Anneli Strobel described how the submitted proposals will be evaluated in 3 steps: Central application, Scientific evaluation and Logistic evaluation, as well as the timing of the results of the evaluation processes.

See appendix 1.

Q&A: questions were raised by the attendees in the Q&A chat and answered by the speakers during the final session of the event.

Table 2: Questions asked during the webinar

QUESTION DETAILS	
1	Where can I find the link to the TAP?
2	If requesting smaller mobile marine infrastructures, do they include the ships to deploy the infrastructures, or should we apply for these also?
3	Does the budget also cover lab consumables, services etc. besides travel and logistics?
4	Can you explain the different roles of the SEP and the anonymous reviewers?

4. Statistics & results

24 participants registered for the webinar training “How to use the Call Application Platform”, and 16 of them attended. The feedback from the participants was positive. All questions asked were addressed immediately during the webinar and added to the [AQUARIUS FAQ page](#). The webinar was recorded and sent to all those who had registered and is available in the [AQUARIUS Training Hub](#) and on [You Tube](#): the video has been viewed 25 times to date.

5. Appendices

5.1. Appendix 1 – Outline and agenda of the webinar

AQUARIUS Training Webinar

27 November 2024, 11:00-12:00 CET

Online

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Agenda

Welcome & Housekeeping 11.00-11.05 CET

Andrea Caburlotto, Moderator

Speakers' presentations 11.05-11.45 CET

Frank Armstrong: AQUARIUS Infrastructure Catalogue

Lorenza Evangelista: AQUARIUS Call Design

Anneli Strobel / Elizabeth De Maio: How to Use the Call Platform

Anneli Strobel: AQUARIUS Evaluation Process

Questions & Answers 11.45-12.00 CET

Housekeeping – About Today's Format

This webinar is being video recorded!

- Cameras & microphones have been disabled
- Questions posted in the Q&A and chat will not be displayed in the video recorded, so your name will not be displayed in the recording

Questions & Answers

- Use the Q&A to ask your questions to the speaker(s)
- Q&A covered during the webinar, along with any that we did not have time to respond to, will be posted on the AQUARIUS webpage

Any problems or comments during or after the session:

hello@aquarius-ri.eu

AQUARIUS Training Webinar

Wednesday, November 27, 11.00-12.00 CET

Agenda

Presentation	Presenter	Time	Duration	Organization
Welcome & Intro	Andrea Caburlotto	11.00 CET	5 Minutes	The National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics (OGS)
AQUARIUS Infrastructure Catalogue	Frank Armstrong	11.05 CET	5 Minutes	Marine Institute (MI)
Call Design & Eligibility Criteria	Lorenza Evangelista	11.10 CET	10 Minutes	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR)
How to use the Call Platform	Anneli Strobel Elisabeth De Maio	11:20 CET	20 Minutes	Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI) INKODE
Evaluation Process	Anneli Strobel	11:40 CET	10 Minutes	Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI)
Q&A Session	All	11:50 CET	10 Minutes	N/A

- Use the Q&A to ask your questions to the speaker(s)
- Q&A covered during the webinar, along with any that we did not have time to respond to, will be posted on the AQUARIUS webpage.
- [FAQ – AQUARIUS](#)
- Thank you for your participation.

AQUARIUS Transnational Funding Call Open 11 November 2024 – 20 January 2025

Open for
applications!

Funding Call
for Transnational Access
to Research Infrastructures

What to do next?

1. Visit aquarius-ri.eu/access/ for all the Call information.
2. Check the eligibility criteria.
3. From November 11, 2024, register on the AQUARIUS Transnational Access Platform (TAP) and activate your account.
4. Check our Research Infrastructure Catalogue and contact the operators to find out whether your proposal can be implemented as planned.
5. Fill in the Transnational Access application form in the TAP.
6. Review and submit your application.

All templates are available on the TAP from 11 November 2024